

Synthesis of 2-Carbomethoxy- and 2-(2-Benzimidazolyl)chromones

K. R. S. REDDY, G. SRIMANNARAYANA* and N. V. SUBBA RAO

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science, Osmanla University, Hyderabad-500 007

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ortho-Hydroxyacetophenones on refluxing with diethyl oxalate in methanol containing sodium methoxide gives methylchromone-2-carboxylate (2). 2 admixed with *o*-phenylenediamine on heating in polyphosphoric acid gives 2-(2-benzimidazolyl)chromone (4) via the anilide (3). Compounds (2-4) inhibited the growth of *A. niger* by 70-80% at 100 ppm.

SEVERAL derivatives of chromone-2-carboxylic acid and 2-(2-benzimidazolyl)chromones have been reported to possess interesting physiological properties. A typical chromone-2-carboxylic acid, disodium chromoglycate was reported to be an effective drug in the treatment of allergic bronchial asthma¹. Another chromone-2-carboxylic acid derivative, *N*-(*p*-sulphamidophenyl)chromone-2-carboxamide was found to be an excellent analgesic, more active than acetylsalicylic acid². Further, heterocyclic benzimidazoles, such as thiazolylbenzimidazole, were reported to exhibit very high antifungal activity against a wide range of foliage diseases³. These considerations prompted us to synthesise methylchromone-2-carboxylate and 2-benzimidazolylchromones and to assess their physiological activity.

The condensation of *ortho*-hydroxyacetophenones and diethyl oxalate was widely used by earlier workers^{4,5} in the synthesis of ethylchromone-2-carboxylates. Making use of this method, sodium methoxide has been employed instead of the sodium ethoxide in the condensation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones (1) and diethyl oxalate; the products were methylchromone-2-carboxylates (2) and not the ethylchromone-2-carboxylates. No attempt was made to isolate the intermediate diketone. The transesterification is complete and evidently the ester-exchange takes place with the substrate diethyl oxalate, and no ethylchromone-2-carboxylate could

be found in tlc from the filtrate after recrystallisation of 2. This phenomenon was already noticed by Ellis⁶ and also in our laboratories⁷. As methylchromone-2-carboxylates are not sufficiently soluble in CDCl₃, the spectra have been recorded¹ in trifluoroacetic acid solutions. The low-field shift of H-3 of the methylchromone-2-carboxylates around δ 7.2 is in agreement with the reported value⁸ for ethylchromone-2-carboxylate in which H-3 resonates at δ 7.13. The ir and uv data are given in Table 1. The ester carbonyl and chromone carbonyl appear around ν_{\max} (nujol) 1 770 and 1 660 cm⁻¹, respectively. The uv absorption spectra reveal an intense band around λ_{\max} (EtOH) 240 nm and less intense band around λ_{\max} (EtOH) 310 nm. The data is in agreement with the earlier reported⁹ data for ethylchromone-2-carboxylate. Thus, the condensation of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones and diethyl oxalate in the presence of sodium methoxide as a basic catalyst is a facile method for the synthesis of methylchromone-2-carboxylate.

By modifying the patented procedure¹⁰, the methylchromone-2-carboxylate (2) was condensed with orthophenylenediamine in polyphosphoric acid (PPA) medium at 170° for 1 h resulted in the corresponding 2-(2-benzimidazolyl)chromones (4). The condensation of methylchromone-2-carboxylate (2a) with *o*-phenylenediamine using polyphosphoric acid at 100° instead of 170° for 4 h, resulted in the isolation of the anilide, 2-[*N*-(*o*-aminophenyl)carba-

TABLE 1—METHYLCHROMONE-2-CARBOXYLATES (2)

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	λ_{\max} (log ϵ) (EtOH)	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	δ (CF ₃ COOH) ppm			CH ₃ in R, R ¹ , R ² (s)
					CO ₂ CH ₃ (s)	H-3 (s)	Ar-H (m)	
2a	120	80	250(3.91), 315(3.52)	1 764, 1 666	8.60	7.00	7.10-8.10	—
2b	148	70	241(4.26), 320(3.79)	1 775, 1 650	3.90	7.33	7.37-8.00	2.30
2c	172	65	235(4.18), 309(3.87)	1 773, 1 664	3.67	7.03	7.15-8.20	2.50
2d	206	80	236(4.24), 307(3.99)	1 770, 1 647	4.16	7.33	7.40-8.20	4.30
2e	234	65	254(4.29), 313(4.13)	1 767, 1 667 1 695	3.75	7.10	7.20-8.00	2.00

Scheme 1

moyl]chromone (3). The anilide (3) was not formed in the absence of PPA.

The methylchromone-2-carboxylates and 2-(2-benzimidazolyl)chromones synthesised above have been tested for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus coli* and *Bacillus subtilis* using tube dilution method and fungistatic activity against *Aspergillus niger* using plate method. 6-Methyl-, 8-methyl-, 7-methoxy-, and 7-amino-2-(2-benzimidazolyl)chromones are active against all the three bacteria at 100 ppm dilution. In general, methylchromone-2-carboxylates seem to be active against *Bacillus coli* only at 100 ppm. It is interesting to note that while 2-(2-benzimidazolyl)chromones have remarkable activity, of the order of 60-80% inhibition at 100 ppm, even methylchromone-2-carboxylates also exhibits considerable activity of the same order. Even at 20 ppm dilution, methylchromone-2-carboxylates and 2-(2-benzimidazolyl)chromones inhibited the growth of fungus to the extent of 50%.

Experimental

The m.p.s. are uncorrected. The uv spectra (EtOH) of the compounds were recorded on a Beck-

man-DB spectrophotometer. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord-132, equipped with sodium chloride cells. The pmr spectra were recorded on a Varian-60 MHz in trifluoroacetic acid using TMS as internal standard. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Methylchromone-2-carboxylates (2): Sodium (2.0 g) was dissolved in dry methanol (25 ml) with stirring. After cooling, a solution of o-hydroxyacetophenone (1) (0.01 mol) in diethyl oxalate (6 ml), methanol (25 ml) and benzene (25 ml) was added to it and the mixture was refluxed for 8 h. After cooling, ether (100 ml) was added. The sodium salt was filtered, washed with anhydrous ether, dissolved in water and the solution acidified. The resultant precipitate was filtered, dried and recrystallised from methanol to yield (2) (Table 1) as colourless needles.

2-(2-Benzimidazolyl)chromones (4): Intimately mixed powder of methylchromone-2-carboxylate (2) (0.005 mol) and o-phenylenediamine (0.005 mol) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (10 g) at 170° for 1 h. After keeping it overnight, it was treated with crushed ice and neutralised with ammonia. The resulting yellow solid, was taken into ethyl acetate and repeatedly extracted with hydrochloric acid (3%). The acid solution was neutralised with ammonia and extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removing the solvent, the yellow substance obtained on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 1) gave 4 as yellow needles. The physical, uv and ir data are presented in Table 2. In the mass spectrum of 4b, M⁺ 276(10) and the base peak at m/z 160 arise due to fission at 2-position, with proton transfer, of chromone and benzimidazole junction. The M⁺ 276 suffers retro-Diels-Alder fragmentation giving m/z 134.

2-N-(o-Aminophenyl)carbamoylchromone (3): 2a (2.0 g) and o-phenylenediamine (1.0 g) were powdered, intimately mixed and heated with polyphosphoric acid (10 g) at 100° for 4 h. After leaving overnight, it was treated with crushed ice and neutralised with ammonia. The deep orange-yellow solid was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethyl acetate to yield 3 as orange-yellow needles. The physical, uv and ir data are presented in Table 2. In the mass spectrum, M⁺ appeared at 280, which itself is base-peak. The

TABLE 2—2-(2-BENZIMIDAZOLYL)CHROMONES (4) AND ITS PRECURSOR (3)

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	λ_{\max} (log ϵ) (EtOH)	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹
4a	224	40	290(4.36), 284(3.95), 338(3.92)	1 684, 1 699
4b	234	30	231(4.34), 280(3.92), 337(3.95)	1 675, 1 693
4c	195	30	280(4.40), 284(3.94), 338(4.22)	1 681, 1 637
4d	222	35	229(4.48), 257(4.22), 279(4.06), 336(4.07)	1 661, 1 613
4e	244	25	290(4.46), 279(3.72), 342(4.32)	1 650, 1 630
3a	292	70	231(4.34), 276(3.96), 436(4.54)	1 692, 1 618

other fragments m/z 121(83) and 160(80) arise due to RDA breakdown with proton transfer.

Conversion of 3a to 4a : 3a (1.0 g) was powdered and heated with polyphosphoric acid (5.0 g) at 170° for 1 h. After leaving it overnight, the reaction mixture was worked up. The yellow substance obtained was recrystallised with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 1) to yield yellow needles of 4a.

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